

The values of stability constants depend to a great extent on the method of investigation, however, it is seen that β , values determined by both the methods of investigation are in close agreement.

The pK value of Monochloroacetic acid and Acetic acid are 2.86 and 4.767 respectively, thus substitution of chlorine decreases the protophilic property of Acetate ion and may therefore, be supposed to be the cause of lesser stability of M.C.A. complexes a compared with Acetate complexes.

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Self condensation of Homophthalic anhydride : Some New Findings*

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3-(2-CARBOXYBENZYL) isocoumarin (III) is reported to have been obtained by (i) refluxing homophthalic anhydride (I) with pyridine and piperidine¹, with quinoline² and with pyridine alone³, (ii) heating homophthalic acid and its anhydride with sodium or potassium acetates^{3,4} and (iii) by pyrolysis of ammonium homophthalate⁵. In the last reaction (III) was obtained as by-product together with homophthalimide that formed the major product.

It is now found that keeping (I) with pyridine alone at room temperature furnishes 4-carboxy-3-(2-carboxybenzyl)-isocoumarin (IV) as a stable substance in a yield exceeding 80%. It smoothly decarboxylates on heating in a metal both at 220° to

give (III). Treatment of (IV) with aq. NaOH in cold followed by acidification gave by decarboxylative hydrolysis the known acetone derivative (VI, R = H) that was earlier obtained by hydrolysis of (III).

Self condensation of (I) would give (II) by acylation (vide mechanism⁶ for acetylation of (I)). It is the rearrangement further of (II) that has given (IV). In the lit. cited above and so also when the present self condensation reaction was heated on boiling water bath, (III) and not (IV) was isolated. This was because the reaction conditions were such that they facilitated decarboxylation of the 4-carboxy group.

The isocoumarin (IV) unlike 4-acylisochromanones⁶ was found to be stable to conc. H₂SO₄, did not give colouration with alc. FeCl₃ and its eq. wt. by titration against aq. NaOH (0.01 N) at 0° showed it to be dibasic. Its possibility to be the isomeric (II) is thus ruled out.

Various reactions of the isocoumarin (III) and the ketone (VI) are already reported¹⁻⁵. The following are the additions. The isocoumarin (III) is found to give the ester (V) in good yield when it is refluxed with MeOH/conc. H₂SO₄ for 3 hr. The same reaction refluxed for 36 hr. is reported⁵ to have yielded a mixture of the ester (V) and the ketone (VII). The ketone (VI) is found to get reduced smoothly with NaBH₄ in methanol at room temperature to furnish, on acidification, 3-(2-carboxybenzyl)-3,4-dihydroisocoumarin (VIII) in good yield. The reduction but at reflux temperature is reported⁴ to have furnished (IX).

Experimental

4-Carboxy-3-(2-carboxybenzyl) isocoumarin (IV): A mixture of homophthalic anhydride (I) (1 g.) and dry pyridine (35 ml.) was well stirred with a magnetic stirrer when it slowly formed a dark brown solution. After leaving it overnight at room temperature, it was poured over crushed ice and HCl. The solid that separated, crystallised from ethyl acetate (charcoal) as heavy plates m.p. 218° (decomp.) yield 0.6 g. (Found: C, 67.0 and H, 4.1%. C₁₈H₁₂O₆ requires C, 66.7 and H, 3.7%); λ_{max}^{MeOH} 230, 275 and 325 nm (log ϵ 4.59, 4.15 and 3.76).

When the above reaction was heated on boiling water bath for 3 hr. and worked up as above, the isocoumarin (III) was obtained that crystallised from dilute methanol in silky needles m.p. and m.m.p. with the authentic specimen¹ 206-7 (Lit.¹ m.p. 210°), yield 0.6 g.

Action of aq. NaOH on (IV): α , α' -Bis-(2-carboxybenzyl) acetone (VI): A solution of the isocoumarin (IV) (1 g.) in aq. NaOH (10 ml., 10%) was left aside at room temperature for half an hour and then acidified with HCl. The solid that separated on scratching (crude yield 0.9 g., m.p. 97°-99°), crystallised from ethyl acetate (charcoal) as colourless needles, m.p. and m.m.p. with the authentic specimen⁵ prepared from (III) 199°-200° (decomp.) (Lit. m.p.

* Part XII of the series Isocoumarins.

199°–200°, 204⁵, 205⁴, 212¹) (Found : C, 68.2; H, 4.9; Calculated for C₁₇H₁₄O₅ : C, 68.4 and H, 4.7).

Partial decarboxylation of (IV) to give (III) : The 4-carboxy-isocoumarin (IV) (0.5 g.) was heated at 220° in a metal bath for 5 min. (evolution of CO₂). The contents, after cooling were repeatedly extracted with ether. Removal of ether from the extract gave a solid that crystallised from dilute methanol as silky needles, m.p. and m.m.p. with the authentic specimen 206°–7°.

The ester (V)-esterification of (III) with MeOH/H₂SO₄ : The isocoumarin (III) (0.5 g.), methanol (30 ml.) and H₂SO₄ (1 ml.) were mixed and refluxed for 2 hr. Methanol (15 ml.) was then removed under reduced pressure and the residue was diluted with water (80 ml.). The sticky product was taken in ether, washed with aq. NaHCO₃. Removal of ether from the extract gave a solid that crystallised from *n*-hexane as colourless needles, m.p. 106°–7° (Lit.⁵ m.p. 107°–9°) (Found : C, 73.7; H, 4.9. C₁₈H₁₅O₄ requires : C, 73.5 and H, 4.76%).

3-(2-Carboxybenzyl)-3,4-dihydroisocoumarin (VIII)-Reduction of (VI) with NaBH₄ : To the ethanolic solution of the ketone (VI) (0.5 g. in 15 ml.), NaBH₄ (0.37 g.) was added in small portions with shaking and the mixture was left aside for 2 hr at room temperature. Crushed ice and conc. HCl were added with stirring till the metallic chlorides dissolved to give a turbid solution that gave a solid on scratching. It crystallised from benzene as clusters of small needles, m.p. 183°–5° (decomp.), yield 0.42 g.

(Lit.¹ m.p. 186°) (Found : C, 72.4; H, 5.2; C₁₇H₁₄O₄ requires : C, 72.4 and H, 4.9%), $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{MeOH}}$ 232, 280 nm (log ϵ 4.12 and 3.24).

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A Note on the Cobalt (II) Chelate of 2,3-dioxo-butyranyl 2-oxime

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RECENTLY, Pathak and Haldar¹ considered the preparation of orange red tris(isonitroso acetophenonato) cobalt(III) from cobalt(II) and isonitroso acetophenone, and observed that it is diamagnetic and its d-d bands are masked by the presence of high intensity pi-pi and charge transfer bands.